

COMT: CO-TRAINING MEAN TEACHERS SEMI-SUPERVISED TRAINING FRAMEWORK FOR CERVICAL SEGMENTATION

Yu Chen¹, Bo Deng¹, Zilun Peng¹, Yongle Zhou¹, Pan Sun¹, Jin Wan¹, Jieyun Bai^{1,2,3 *}

¹College of Information Science and Technology, Jinan University, Guangzhou, 510632, China

²Guangdong Provincial Key Laboratory of Traditional Chinese Medicine Information Technology, Jinan University, Guangzhou 510632, China

³Auckland Bioengineering Institute, University of Auckland, Auckland, 1010, New Zealand

*Corresponding author: jbai996@aucklanduni.ac.nz

ABSTRACT

Cervical morphology is essential for evaluating gynecological health, and accurate segmentation of cervical muscles in transvaginal ultrasound (TVUS) images is crucial for analyzing cervical anatomy and function. However, the low resolution and noise in ultrasound images make manual labeling time-consuming. Existing semi-supervised medical image segmentation methods primarily focus on generating additional supervisory signals from unlabeled images. This paper proposes a semi-supervised deep learning framework based on MeanTeacher, which utilizes different model architectures to enhance diversity in unlabeled images and applies minimum entropy to reconstruct pseudo-soft labels. Experiments on the ISBI FUGC 2025 dataset demonstrate the effectiveness of this method, contributing to early risk prediction and personalized treatment in clinical decision-making.

Index Terms— Image segmentation, Semi-supervised learning, Deep learning, Cervix, Ultrasound, Gynecology

1. INTRODUCTION

Precise segmentation of anatomical structures in medical imaging is essential for accurate diagnosis and effective treatment. In gynecology, transvaginal ultrasound (TVUS) is widely used to evaluate cervical morphology, a key factor in predicting preterm birth. Accurate cervical segmentation facilitates early prediction and improves clinical management. However, manual annotation is time-consuming and prone to errors due to image noise and low resolution.

Recent advances in deep learning have significantly improved medical image analysis, especially segmentation tasks. CNN-based models such as U-Net [1] and its variants [2, 3, 4, 5, 6], along with transformer-based models like Swin-Unet [7], have been widely applied. Yet, fully supervised models require large annotated datasets, particularly for data-intensive architectures like transformers. The labor-intensive nature of expert annotation limits broader clinical use.

To address this, semi-supervised learning (SSL) has emerged as a promising solution, leveraging limited labeled data with abundant unlabeled data to reduce annotation costs while maintaining strong performance. Self-training with pseudo-labels is a well-established SSL approach. Yang et al. [8] demonstrated strong performance with ST and ST++ models using strong data augmentation (SDA). However, medical images are often more sensitive to augmentation than natural images. Other studies [9, 10] introduced adversarial losses from discriminators to guide unlabeled training, though stabilizing joint training remains challenging. Contrastive learning [11] has also been adopted to enhance representation learning, though its generalizability needs further validation. Among SSL strategies, consistency regularization, such as the mean teacher model [12], remains dominant.

Recent advancements in semi-supervised medical image segmentation (SSMIS) have shown remarkable progress, particularly in mean teacher-based approaches. UA-MT [13] proposes an uncertainty-aware training framework to mitigate the adverse effects of learning from pseudo-labeled samples. AD-MT [14] utilizes random updates to the teacher model parameters along with conflict-based learning to implement a diversified teaching strategy, achieving state-of-the-art (SOTA) performance in medical image segmentation tasks. Moreover, Luo et al. [15] found that exploiting the differences in learning paradigms between CNN- and Transformer-based segmentation models for cross-teaching can produce remarkable results, significantly inspiring our research.

In this paper, we propose a semi-supervised deep learning framework for the segmentation of cervix in TVUS images. Our contributions are as follows: (1) We introduce a co-training mean-teacher pair framework (CO-MT) that incorporates diversified perspectives from different models while ensuring the stability of EMA updates; (2) We design a pseudo-label reconstruction module based on minimizing pixel classification entropy, which maximizes the utilization of unlabeled images and reduces the impact of noise; (3) We validate the effectiveness of our method through experiments on the

ISBI FUGC 2025 transvaginal ultrasound cervical segmentation dataset.

2. METHODOLOGY

SSMIS can be defined as follows: The available dataset is divided into labeled data \mathcal{X} and unlabeled data \mathcal{U} . Due to the pixel-dense nature of segmentation annotations, the amount of unlabeled data is typically much larger than labeled data (i.e., $|\mathcal{U}| \gg |\mathcal{X}|$). During training, the objective of SSMIS is to construct an effective segmentation model by leveraging both labeled and unlabeled data with a batch of labeled samples $\mathcal{X} = \{(x_i, y_i)\}$ and a batch of unlabeled samples $\mathcal{U} = \{u_j\}$. The overall architecture of our semi-supervised training framework is shown in Figure 1.

2.1. Co-training with Mean Teacher

Inspired by the work of Luo et al. [15], models from different architectures have different feature extraction capabilities, providing diverse perspectives for learning from unlabeled data. Our co-training Mean Teacher framework builds on this idea by incorporating a teacher network updated through exponential smoothing of the student network weights. During training, averaging network weights typically results in more accurate and stable predictions than directly using the final model weights, thereby combining the advantages of both methods. This generates in pseudo-labels for semi-supervised learning that are both diverse and less noisy. Additionally, since the teacher network weights are updated through exponential smoothing of the student network weights, no additional gradient computation is needed:

$$\theta_T \leftarrow \alpha \theta_T + (1 - \alpha) \theta_S. \quad (1)$$

Here, α is the smoothing coefficient hyperparameter, θ_T represents the weights of the teacher network, and θ_S represents the weights of the student network.

The total loss of the CO-MT training framework \mathcal{L}_{total} is the sum of the losses from two separately trained networks \mathcal{L}_{f_θ} , where each network’s loss consists of both supervised and semi-supervised losses, \mathcal{L}_{sup} , $\lambda \mathcal{L}_{semi}$:

$$\mathcal{L}_{ctl} = \underbrace{\mathcal{L}_{sup}^1 + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{semi}^1}_{\text{Target network}} + \underbrace{\mathcal{L}_{sup}^2 + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{semi}^2}_{\text{Auxiliary network}}. \quad (2)$$

In widespread applications, λ is a weighting factor defined by a time-varying Gaussian function. Specifically, it is given by: $\lambda(t) = 0.1 \cdot e^{-5(1 - \frac{t_i}{t_{total}})^2}$, where t_i denotes the current training iteration and t_{total} is the total number of iterations. For labeled data, i.e., supervised training, the loss function is constructed as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{sup} = \mathcal{L}_{ce}(\hat{y}_i, y_i) + \mathcal{L}_{dice}(\hat{y}_i, y_i). \quad (3)$$

\mathcal{L}_{ce} and \mathcal{L}_{dice} represent the cross-entropy loss and dice loss, respectively. \hat{y}_i and y_i represent the prediction and label of image x_i , respectively. For unlabeled data, i.e. semi-supervised training, the loss is constructed as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{semi} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \beta (y_i^j - \hat{y}_i^j)^2. \quad (4)$$

In fact, this is a weighted MSE loss, where β represents the loss weight and n is the product of the number of pixels and classes. The y_i here differs from the previous one, as it comes from the reconstructed pseudo-labels. The details of pseudo-label reconstruction and the weight β will be addressed later.

2.2. Pseudo-label Reconstruction

In traditional Mean Teacher, pseudo-labels for unlabeled samples are directly derived from the teacher model’s predictions. However, these pseudo-labels are not the true labels and always contain noise. Some MT-based approaches [13, 14] focus on mitigating the impact of this noise. Building on this, we reconstruct pseudo-labels using a prediction entropy minimization strategy to fully exploit the perspectives from different models.

The reliability of a prediction on a pixel can be measured by entropy, where low entropy indicates reliable predictions, and high entropy indicates unreliable predictions. The calculation of prediction entropy is given as follows:

$$\mathcal{H}(\hat{y}_i) = - \sum_{i=1}^C \hat{y}_i \log \hat{y}_i. \quad (5)$$

Here C denotes the number of channels in the predicted results, which corresponds to the number of classes. By calculating the prediction entropy maps of the pseudo-labels generated by two teacher models, we apply the entropy minimization strategy to reconstruct the pseudo-labels as the final supervision signal. This is represented by the following:

$$\hat{y}_T(p) = \begin{cases} \hat{y}_T^1(p) & \text{if } \mathcal{H}(\hat{y}_T^1(p)) \geq \mathcal{H}(\hat{y}_T^2(p)) \\ \hat{y}_T^2(p) & \text{if } \mathcal{H}(\hat{y}_T^1(p)) < \mathcal{H}(\hat{y}_T^2(p)). \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

This means that for each pixel p , we select the smallest pseudo-soft label value from the corresponding pixel positions in the two pseudo-labels \hat{y}_T^1 and \hat{y}_T^2 as the final supervision signal \hat{y}_T .

2.3. Entropy Adaptation Loss Weights

The reconstruction module designed above enables mutual correction of pseudo-labels from different perspectives, but it does not fully resolve the issue. In challenging regions, such as boundary segmentation, pseudo-labels from two different perspectives still exhibit high prediction entropy in these areas. Therefore, we apply conservative learning to the high-entropy regions after label reconstruction to further reduce the

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed framework CO-MT. The approach focuses on efficiently utilizing unlabeled samples by constructing teacher-student pairs, which ensure stable updates in semi-supervised learning while providing diverse perspectives for pseudo-label reconstruction.

impact of noise in these areas:

$$\beta = \exp(-\mu \cdot \mathcal{H}(\hat{y}_T(p))) + b. \quad (7)$$

The parameter μ controls the scaling of the entropy term, while the bias term b ensures that the weights remains bounded. Through this exponential decay reduction based on predicted entropy, we can provide conservative losses for the challenging classification regions.

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1. Dataset

We used the ISBI FUGC 2025 dataset for the experiments, which consists of 590 transvaginal ultrasound images of the cervix after bladder emptying, each with a size of 336x544 (500 images for training and 90 for testing). These images capture cervical anatomy, specifically the anterior and posterior lips of the cervix. The training set contains 50 labeled ultrasound images, while the remaining 450 images are unlabeled and used as unannotated data.

3.2. Implementation Details

All experiments were conducted using PyTorch on an NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU. We employed the AdamW optimizer to update the network parameters (weight decay = 0.1) with an initial learning rate of 0.001, and used a cosine learning rate schedule. A total of 450 epochs were trained. The batch size was 10, consisting 5 labeled images and 5 unlabeled images. During training, the data augmentation strategy for the teacher network input included basic augmentations such

as random gamma correction, random cutout, random horizontal flipping, and random rotation. The student network input was augmented further with color enhancements. For model selection, to align with practical applications, we used a lightweight U-Net (initial channels = 16, 2.16M parameters, 11.63G FLOPs) and employed Deeplabv3 [16] as the auxiliary co-training network with pre-trained weights.

3.3. Comparison with Other Methods

Table 1: Quantitative performance comparison of different methods for cervical segmentation on FUGC dataset.

Methods	Type	Dice \uparrow (%)	HD \downarrow
U-Net [1]	LabeledOnly	79.68	56.89
ST [8]	Self-Training	82.77	55.83
ST++ [8]	Self-Training	81.28	91.80
AdvSemi [9]	Adv-Training	77.86	62.79
Hu et al. [11]	Contrast-Learning	84.81	56.80
UA-MT [13]	MT-Based	72.88	53.93
AD-MT [14]	MT-Based	89.65	31.49
Ours	MT-Based	91.23	29.20

We use two metrics to quantitatively evaluate our method, including Dice and the Hausdorff Distance (HD). To demonstrate the validity of the proposed approach, we compared our approach with a baseline and six different semi-supervised approaches. Among all methods, our MT-based approach achieves the best performance, attaining the highest Dice coefficient of 91.23% and the lowest Hausdorff Distance (HD) of 29.20. Specifically, The advsemi method based on

adversarial training performed worse than the LabeledOnly baseline, suggesting it may not be suitable for this segmentation task. The self-training approach shows limited advantages, possibly due to noisy pseudo-labels leading to incorrect knowledge during subsequent training. In comparison, the model pre-trained with contrastive learning performs better, with a 5.13 higher Dice score than the baseline. Among the six comparison methods, the recent SOTA method AD-MT performs the best, with a 9.97 higher Dice score and a 25.43 lower HD than the baseline. (Table 1)

3.4. Ablation Experiments and Sensitivity Analysis

Table 2: Results of ablation experiments conducted on the FUGC dataset.

CoT	EMA	PR	β	Dice \uparrow (%)	HD \downarrow
\times	\checkmark	\times	\times	88.69	34.57
\checkmark	\times	\times	\times	90.67	52.10
\checkmark	\checkmark	\times	\times	91.25	33.37
\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	\times	89.60	<u>32.27</u>
\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	<u>91.23</u>	29.20

Table 2 presents our ablation experiments examining the effectiveness of key components in our model: auxiliary network co-training (CoT), teacher network updates via EMA, Pseudo-label Reconstruction (PR), and entropy-based adaptive loss weighting (β). The results show that the best performance is achieved with the combination of all components, yielding a Dice score of 91.23% and an HD of 29.20. By incorporating CoT, EMA further improves the semi-supervised segmentation model, with the reconstructed pseudo-labels reducing the HD value, although not optimizing the Dice score. The use of a weighted semi-supervised loss further refines the supervisory signal, leading to optimal overall segmentation performance.

(a) Sensitivity Analysis on μ (a) Sensitivity Analysis on b

Fig. 2: Sensitivity Analysis on the hyper-parameters of Entropy Adaptation Loss Weights

As shown in Table 3, we evaluated the impact of different auxiliary networks on cervical vertebra segmentation

Table 3: Quantitative performance comparison of different auxiliary network for cervical segmentation the FUGC dataset.

Aux-Models	Params(M)	GFLOPs	Dice \uparrow (%)	HD \downarrow
U-Net (16)	2.16M	11.63	90.87	30.24
U-Net (32)	8.64M	46.01	88.86	34.73
U-Net (64)	34.53M	182.99	90.84	29.70
U-Lite	0.88M	2.21	91.68	28.18
UNeXt	1.47M	1.64	90.62	31.56
TinyU-Net	0.48M	4.79	89.31	31.92
DeepLabv3				
-mobilenet	11.02M	6.95	90.81	37.33
-resnet50	42.00M	121.19	<u>91.23</u>	<u>29.20</u>
-resnet101	60.99M	175.58	90.91	30.35

performance using the FUGC dataset. The traditional U-Net performed consistently across different scales (16/32/64). Among lightweight architectures, UNeXt achieved competitive results (91.68% and 28.18% Dice). The more complex DeepLabv3, with a higher parameter count, delivered efficient performance. Overall, our proposed method showed stable results, and auxiliary networks with different architectures generally provided better performance than those closely aligned with the target segmentation model.

To validate the effectiveness of our entropy adaptation loss weights, we conducted sensitivity analyses on two key hyperparameters μ and b , as shown in Fig. 2. For μ steps, We observe that better model performance occurs at $\mu=1.0$, achieving the highest Dice score while maintaining a high HD. The performance degrades when μ deviates from this optimal point, with both smaller (0.5, 0.8) and larger (1.5) values leading to decreased segmentation accuracy. Similarly, for the b parameter, the model exhibits peak performance at $b=0.5$, where it achieves the highest Dice score and lowest HD simultaneously. The performance shows a gradual decline as b approaches either 0 or 1, demonstrating the importance of appropriate parameter selection for optimal model performance.

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, we present a novel semi-supervised deep learning framework, CO-MT, for accurate cervical segmentation in transvaginal ultrasound (TVUS) images. By leveraging a co-training approach with Mean Teacher, our framework effectively incorporates diversified perspectives from different model architectures to stabilize and enhance the learning process. Additionally, the proposed pseudo-label reconstruction module, based on minimizing pixel classification entropy, further enhances segmentation performance by reducing noise in the predictions. Experiments on the ISBI FUGC 2025 dataset

demonstrate the effectiveness of our method, achieving state-of-the-art results in cervical segmentation. This approach not only addresses the challenges of limited labeled data but also holds potential for broader applications in clinical practice, facilitating early detection of high-risk pregnancies and more accurate clinical decision-making. Future work will focus on refining the framework to better handle challenging regions and exploring its applicability to other medical imaging tasks.

5. COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

This research study was conducted retrospectively using human subject data made available in open access by the ISBI FUGC 2025 challenge. Ethical approval was not required as confirmed by the license attached with the open access data.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, “U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation,” in *Medical image computing and computer-assisted intervention—MICCAI 2015: 18th international conference, Munich, Germany, October 5-9, 2015, proceedings, part III 18*. Springer, 2015, pp. 234–241.
- [2] J. Chen, R. Chen, W. Wang, J. Cheng, L. Zhang, and L. Chen, “Tinyu-net: Lighter yet better u-net with cascaded multi-receptive fields,” in *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*. Springer, 2024, pp. 626–635.
- [3] B.-D. Dinh, T.-T. Nguyen, T.-T. Tran, and V.-T. Pham, “1m parameters are enough? a lightweight cnn-based model for medical image segmentation,” in *2023 Asia Pacific Signal and Information Processing Association Annual Summit and Conference (APSIPA ASC)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1279–1284.
- [4] Z. Han, M. Jian, and G.-G. Wang, “Convunext: An efficient convolution neural network for medical image segmentation,” *Knowledge-based systems*, vol. 253, pp. 109512, 2022.
- [5] F. Tang, J. Ding, Q. Quan, L. Wang, C. Ning, and S. K. Zhou, “Cmunext: An efficient medical image segmentation network based on large kernel and skip fusion,” in *2024 IEEE International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–5.
- [6] J. M. J. Valanarasu and V. M. Patel, “Unext: Mlp-based rapid medical image segmentation network,” in *International conference on medical image computing and computer-assisted intervention*. Springer, 2022, pp. 23–33.
- [7] H. Cao, Y. Wang, J. Chen, D. Jiang, X. Zhang, Q. Tian, and M. Wang, “Swin-unet: Unet-like pure transformer for medical image segmentation,” in *European conference on computer vision*. Springer, 2022, pp. 205–218.
- [8] L. Yang, W. Zhuo, L. Qi, Y. Shi, and Y. Gao, “St++: Make self-training work better for semi-supervised semantic segmentation,” in *CVPR*, 2022.
- [9] W.-C. Hung, Y.-H. Tsai, Y.-T. Liou, Y.-Y. Lin, and M.-H. Yang, “Adversarial learning for semi-supervised semantic segmentation,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.07934*, 2018.
- [10] F. Zhao, Y. Chen, K. Huang, X. He, X. Chen, and Y. Hou, “Semi-bgsegnet: A semi-supervised boundary-guided breast tumor segmentation network,” in *2023 IEEE 20th International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–5.
- [11] X. Hu, D. Zeng, X. Xu, and Y. Shi, “Semi-supervised contrastive learning for label-efficient medical image segmentation,” in *Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention—MICCAI 2021: 24th International Conference, Strasbourg, France, September 27–October 1, 2021, Proceedings, Part II 24*. Springer, 2021, pp. 481–490.
- [12] A. Tarvainen and H. Valpola, “Mean teachers are better role models: Weight-averaged consistency targets improve semi-supervised deep learning results,” *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 30, 2017.
- [13] L. Yu, S. Wang, X. Li, C.-W. Fu, and P.-A. Heng, “Uncertainty-aware self-ensembling model for semi-supervised 3d left atrium segmentation,” in *Medical image computing and computer assisted intervention—MICCAI 2019: 22nd international conference, Shenzhen, China, October 13–17, 2019, proceedings, part II 22*. Springer, 2019, pp. 605–613.
- [14] Z. Zhao, Z. Wang, L. Wang, D. Yu, Y. Yuan, and L. Zhou, “Alternate diverse teaching for semi-supervised medical image segmentation,” in *European Conference on Computer Vision*. Springer, 2024, pp. 227–243.
- [15] X. Luo, M. Hu, T. Song, G. Wang, and S. Zhang, “Semi-supervised medical image segmentation via cross teaching between cnn and transformer,” in *International conference on medical imaging with deep learning*. PMLR, 2022, pp. 820–833.
- [16] L.-C. Chen, G. Papandreou, F. Schroff, and H. Adam, “Rethinking atrous convolution for semantic image segmentation,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 2017, pp. 889–897.